

Preparation of 5-Aryl-4-Arylimino-6-Benzylimino-2-Phenylimino-1,3,5-Dithiazine

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Manuscript received 11 December 1983, revised 25 October 1983, accepted 3 December 1983

Several 5-aryl-4-arylimino-6-benzylimino-2-phenylimino-1,3,5-dithiazines (III) have been prepared by the interaction of phenyl isocyanodichloride and 1,3,5-trisubstituted-2,4-dithiobiurets.

RECENTLY, phenyl isocyanodichloride has been used in the synthesis of 1,3,5-triazines^{1,2}. The present communication describes the synthesis of certain 1,3,5-dithiazines.

The interaction of phenyl isocyanodichloride (I)³ and 1,3-diphenyl-2,4-dithiobiurets (IIa)⁴ in boiling benzene/chloroform medium afforded an unstable dark redish yellow solid (IIIa), m.p. 98° (d). The product was found non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. Odour of phenyl isothiocyanate was noticed on pyrolysis. It decomposed when heated with conc. hydrochloric acid and benzylamine. The ir spectrum of the product indicated presence of bands due to $\nu(C=N)$ at 1620, amide (II) band at 1490, C-N stretching at 1300 and C-S-C band at 690 cm^{-1} ^{5,6}. The nmr spectrum of the product indicated the signals due to methylene protons of benzyl group (δ 4.43 ppm) and also the phenyl protons between δ 6.9-7.6 ppm.

Structure III can arise because of two thiol (-SH) groups are available for the reaction.

where (a) R=R'=phenyl, (b) R=R'=m-tolyl, (c) R=R'=p-tolyl, (d) R=R'=m-chlorophenyl and Bz=benzyl

Several other 1,3,5-dithiazines (IIIb-III d) have been prepared by the extension of this method (Table 1). Incidentally, these could not be isomerised into the related 1,3,5-triazines.

Experimental

5-Aryl-4-arylimino-6-benzylimino-2-phenylimino-1,3,5-dithiazines (III): Details of a typical experiment (where aryl=phenyl) are as follows.

TABLE 1—PREPARATION OF 5-ARYL-4-ARYLIMINO-6-BENZYLIMINO-2-PHENYLIMINO-1,3,5-DITHIAZINES (III)
Solvent: Dry benzene

Sl. No.	1,3,5-Substituted-2,4-dithiobiuret (II) (g)	g.	m.p. (°C)	-1,3,5-Dithiazine (III)	
				Analysis % ; Found/Calcd.	
				N	S
1.	1,3-Diphenyl-5-benzyl (IIa) (7.5)	4.5	98 (d)	12.30 (11.79)	13.86 (13.39)
2.	1,3-Di-m-tolyl-5-benzyl (IIb) (8.1)	4.6	108 (d)	11.65 (11.09)	13.01 (12.69)
3.	1,3-Di-p-tolyl-5-benzyl (IIc) (8.1)	4.8	113 (d)	11.73 (11.09)	13.24 (12.69)
4.	1,3-Di-m-Chloro-phenyl-5-benzyl (II d) (8.9)	4.7	116 (d)	10.84 (10.25)	12.95 (11.72)

To a benzene suspension of 1,3-diphenyl-5-benzyl-2,4-dithiobiuret⁴ (7.5 g; 0.02 mole, in 50 ml) was added phenyl isocyanodichloride³ (4 g; >0.02 mole) and the mixture was refluxed for 5 hr. Evolution of hydrogen chloride was clearly detected. On evaporation of the solvent followed by trituration of the semi-solid residue several times with petroleum ether (60-80°), an unstable redish yellow product (IIIa) (4.5 g), m.p. 98° (d) (Found: N, 12.30; S, 13.86. C₂₈H₂₂N₄S₂ requires N, 11.78; S, 13.39%) was isolated.

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the author are due to Prof. K. N. Munshi, Head, Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur for facilities. One of the authors (P.P.P.) thanks Dr. B. B. Sundaresan, Director, N.E.E.R.I., for permission to carry out this work.

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